

Recommended citation: Bernhard, J., Davidsen, J., Ryberg, T., A.-K. Carstensen, , & Rafn Abildgaard, J. (2018). Engineering students' shared experiences and joint problem solving in collaborative learning. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 597-604). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672635.

Engineering students' shared experiences and joint problem solving in collaborative learning

J Bernhard¹

Professor

Linköping University

Norrköping, Sweden

E-mail: jonte.bernhard@liu.se

J Davidsen

Assistant Professor

Aalborg University

Aalborg, Denmark

E-mail: jdavidsen@hum.aau.dk

T Ryberg

Professor

Aalborg University

Aalborg, Denmark

E-mail: ryberg@hum.aau.dk

A-K Carstensen

Senior Lecturer

Jönköping University

Jönköping, Sweden

E-mail: Anna-Karin.Carstensen@ju.se

J Rafn Abildgaard

Research Assistant

Aalborg University

Aalborg, Denmark

E-mail: jra@plan.aau.dk

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Teaching Creativity and Innovation, Discipline-specific Teaching and Learning

Keywords: Collaborative learning, video ethnography, interaction analysis

¹ Corresponding Author: J Bernhard, jonte.bernhard@liu.se

INTRODUCTION

In engineering education students' are commonly expected to think and learn collaboratively [1, 2] in, for example, problem-based-learning (PBL), design projects, and lab-work. Thinking collaboratively is seen as a critical and creative process that leads to deep and meaningful learning experiences and outcomes. Collaboration implies a shared activity and should thus not be conflated with co-operation there the latter also represents individual contributions to a common task, but without the shared influence from the members of a group. Spoken language is commonly seen as the primary resource for engaging in collaborative learning [3], while other resources are seen as secondary. These often overlooked resources are ephemeral (gestures, body-movements, etc.) or present in tangible media (models, foam, etc. showing ideas of individual and collaborative thinking.

Despite the importance given to collaborative learning in engineering education, students' collaborative learning *processes* in naturalistic educational settings have been given little attention in previous research. The aim of this study has been to explore what interactional work student teams do in collaborative learning settings such as PBL and lab-work? What kind of resources do student teams use to collaborate and complete tasks? What is the role of the resources used?

1 BACKGROUND AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Studies have shown that representations and drawings are crucial in mediating different understandings among group members in engineering education [4]. According to Juhl and Lindegaard [4] talk, observations and ideas are often inscribed into two-dimensional representations capturing ideas or design proposals. Whereas Juhl and Lindegaard study representations as static products of individual and collective work, we focus on the process of making use of various representations/knowledge objects in students' collaborative thinking. This theoretical perspective is informed by embodied interaction analysis [5] and socio cultural theories highlighting the importance of mediating artefacts in thinking and collective reasoning [6]. As discussed by, for example, Davidsen and Ryberg [3] collaboration is more than language and should integrate a view on the bodily-material resources, also in studies of engineering education. This stance emphasise that collaborative thinking, also in engineering education, is haptic, kinaesthetic, visual, and spatial, not only verbal and linguistic, or logical and mathematical [7].

2 METHODOLOGY AND SETTING

To investigate the aim of this study students' courses of action have been recorded using video in a PBL-project at Aalborg University (AAU), Denmark, and in lab-work in a high-frequency electronics course at Linköping University (LiU), Sweden.

2.1 Aalborg University

At AAU collaborative problem-based projects performed by groups of students (typically 5 – 6 in a group) in the PBL-based Architecture and Design programme have been studied. In this paper we present a study of a group of six students (4

female, 2 male) in their sixth semester. They have the task of designing a real office building for an external partner in a large city in Denmark and in the session analysed they are preparing for a status seminar the next day. The interaction within this and other groups has been recorded using multiple video cameras during complete sessions – in this case the session lasted almost 6 hours. To facilitate analysis, recordings have been synchronized – the still photo in Fig. 1 shows an example of how the interactions within the group have been recorded by five cameras (including one body-mounted GoPro camera).

Fig. 1. Excerpt from synchronized video recordings that shows one group of students seen from multiple cameras. All pictures display the groups' activities at the *same* time, but from different viewpoints. In the lower middle picture, one student points to a detail in a drawing while the group discusses a design decision.

2.2 Linköping University

At LiU, students' courses of action in labwork (typically 2 – 3 students in a group) in one course in high-frequency electronics has been studied [8]. The interaction within a group during has been recorded using a single video camera.

2.3 Interaction analysis

As described above students' activities were recorded using digital camcorders. These data were subsequently used to detect typical interaction patterns and find evidence supporting, or refuting, hypotheses regarding the generality of these patterns [9]. We have in particular been looking for how the students were actually working together, what they did, what resources they used, what they made relevant, and how they oriented themselves towards the object of learning. This means that our primary unit of analysis was the activities of the groups. After repeated viewings, some episodes were found to contain more interesting and comparable activities in relation to our aim. Particularly interesting parts of these episodes were transcribed to allow for detailed examination of interactional patterns. In the transcriptions, standard conventions used in conversation analysis have been used [10] and transcripts included in this paper were ultimately translated into English. Pseudonyms have been used for students' names.

3 FINDINGS

As the space is limited it is only possible for us to present two short excerpts from our analysis of video data in this paper: One from the PBL group at AAU and one from the high frequency electronics lab at LiU. We have made a much more extensive analysis of the videos and have selected the episodes described below as they were representative and illustrative for what we found during our analysis. I.e., similar episodes to these we are describing here exist throughout the analysed interactions. In total we have recorded students' activities using digital camcorders, resulting in 1,000 hours of video from PBL-projects at AAU and 400 hours of video observation at LiU from lab-work in electronics and electric circuit theory. In addition to these recordings students' learning in mechanics labs have also been studied at LiU using video [11].

3.1 PBL at Aalborg University

The groups in this PBL design project have their own designated working space – resembling what architects traditionally refer to as a studio. As can be seen in Fig. 1 the boards surrounding the working space (and serving as dividers to other groups working spaces) are cluttered with drawings, sketches, photographs, and sticky notes. These serve as a historical trajectory of materials and design ideas and are constantly present to the student group.

Fig. 2. a) Mette demonstrates (see turn 1 in excerpt 1) the passage. b) Mette points to a detail in a drawing (turn 12). The 3D foam model is also visible in this picture.

Immediately before excerpt 1 starts the students are discussing how to address design problems. A 3D model consisting of different separate layers made by foam is fetched by Mette. Heidi with support of Sine proposes that the top floor of the buildings should be slightly dislocated to complete the shape of the building. Mette takes up Heidi's suggestion and in turn 1 and Fig. 2a it is shown how she demonstrates how this solution might work.

Excerpt 1 (See also Fig. 2a – 2b):

- | | | | |
|----|--------|--|--|
| 1. | Mette: | with a passage all way around and then | Mette dislocates the top floor in the 3D foam model and indicates with a hand movement the location of a passage. See Fig. 2a. |
| 2. | Heidi: | but I also think (.) what you now (.) if you imagine this are you dragging- then you could also imagine the you drag the window tiers in well so there still is a roof sticking out over so you created an possibility for staying | First points on a drawing on the iPad and thereafter on the 3D foam model. |
| 3. | Ina: | yeah | At the same time Mette |

- | | | | |
|-----|--------|--|--|
| 4. | Sine: | yeah precisely | fetches a drawing on paper. |
| 5. | Heidi: | for example (if one had it here) | |
| 6. | Ina: | that could also work | |
| 7. | (1.9) | | |
| 8. | Heidi: | yeah but | Points on the 3D-foam model. |
| 9. | Ina: | is it | |
| 10. | Heidi: | here here is the window (.) but there is still a roof here for example and then you actually have a room up here | Points on the 3D-foam model. |
| 11. | Ina: | yes (.) and it was actually therefore | Moves closer and points on the 3D-foam model |
| 12. | Mette: | I was in doubt that you meant (.) so with window bands on | Points in drawing. See Fig. 2b. |
| 13. | Heidi: | eh:: yes if one imagine something there also | Also points in the drawing. |
| 14. | Sven: | (it makes) you to pull it back | |
| 15. | Ina: | but you keep the shape | |
| 16. | Heidi: | the window is maybe actually (0.6) here | Points on the 3D-foam model. |

The students' discussion of the advantages and disadvantages of the solution with a dislocated top floor continues for some while after turn 16. In this discussion ample use of the 3D foam model is made and its 3D features is supporting their collaborative thinking. In the excerpt it can be seen that gestures [12] are used indexically by a speaker to indicate what she is referring to or to demonstrate a feature of the imagined and concrete building. Although not visible in this excerpt, the students also used gestures to make "gestured drawings" [13] in the air to substitute for making a quick sketch or for enhancing an argument. Furthermore, the students made extensive use of drawings made by hand on paper or made on an iPad or computer as well as quick sketches on paper in parallel with the ongoing discussions. Moreover, from the excerpt one can get the impression that only the female students are active (e.g. talking and gesturing a lot). However, investigating the whole session this is not true and in Fig. 1 one can actually see the male students active in the background.

3.2 Electronics labwork at Linköping University

In the lab sequence analysed the task students are facing is to make measurements on several circuits consisting of unknown elements and to model this circuit. For measurements a digital oscilloscope is used. The oscilloscope is connected to a computer enabling the results to also be displayed on the computer screen. A complication for the students in solving this task is that in RF-electronics many of the idealization assumptions on which basic electric circuit theory and electronics are not valid.

Excerpt 2 (See also Fig. 3a – 3d):

- | | | | |
|-----|-------|--|--|
| 17. | Leif: | it is (.) it ends like it is short circuited | Points to the oscilloscope with his left hand index finger. See Fig. 3a. |
| 18. | Rune: | m:: | |
| 19. | Leif: | is blocked | |
| 20. | Rune: | m:: | |
| 21. | (1.6) | | |
| 22. | Leif: | this would mean that we have (.) a coil | |

	(.) a capacitor	
23.	(10.5)	Leif makes a sketch in his scribbling pad
24.	Leif: right	
25.	(6.7)	Rune points to something in the sketch
26.	Leif: it should be something like that	
27.	(3.7)	
28.	Leif: high (.) low frequencies	Points with the left hand index finger in the oscilloscope picture. See Fig. 3b
	(.) high	Moves the index finger towards the flank. Fig 3b.
	(.) in between some (.) some rattle	Moves the index finger back and forth between the two previous indications.
29.	(2.4)	
30.	Leif: here we have (.) the positive flank	Points with a pen in his right hand to the flank and moves the pen up and down. See Fig. 3c.
31.	(4.2)	
32.	Rune: (yes that we know)	
33.	Leif: up to here	Distinctly point with the pen to the end of the flank. Fig. 3c.
34.	Rune: Yes	
35.	(2.2)	
36.	Rune: we get up (.) well then we had a coil and a capacitor	Make a sweeping hand movement along the measured graph. See Fig. 3d

Fig. 3. The oscilloscope is seen in the upper left corner and the measurements are also displayed on the computer screen. *a)* Leif is responding to Rune in turn 17. *b)* Leif indicate the high and low frequency characteristics in turn 28. *c)* Leif indicates the flank in turns 30 – 33. *d)* Rune suggests in turn 36 that the circuit consists of a coil and a capacitance. *e)* Shows how the oscilloscope graph looks on the computer and in Figure 3e it is also shown how Leif points to the peak as a confirmation of the idea of a coil and a capacitance.

For about a minute the students are continuing discussing the circuit, go back to a previous measurement on another circuit to compare, and make some sketches. Finally they feel confident that the circuit consists of a coil and a capacitor and as a confirmation Leif points to the peak as displayed in Figure 3e and moves the pen as is indicated by the arrow.

Similar to the PBL-students gestures are important in Leif's and Rune's interactions. Both for pointing and for making "gestured drawings". An additional resource used by Leif and Rune were to use a computer to make simulations.

4 DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS, AND IMPLICATIONS

The use of video ethnographic and embodied interaction analysis methods in this study have made it possible for us to do a fine-grained investigation of the interactional work students do and the resources they use to collaborate and to complete tasks as teams. This has enabled the study *in situ* of how students' daily activities are materially, bodily, and interactionally organized, as well as of details of individuals' actions and the conceptual and material resources used. As there is a lack of studies in engineering education research attempting to do this our study demonstrates the feasibility of the method.

The two educational settings briefly described in this paper could, on a first impression, seem to be rather different. However, the communalities found in our analysis are striking. In both cases the use of a wealth of bodily-material resources are an integral and seamless part of students' interactions and they are used by students in their joint production of understanding and imagining. Bodily resources (e.g. gestures, utterances, bodily orientations), concrete materials (e.g. 3D-foam models, paper models, real circuits), "low-tech" inscriptions (e.g. sketches, drawings on paper, sticky notes) and "high-tech" inscription devices (e.g. CAD-drawings, digital oscilloscopes, computer simulations). The use of these resources is heavily interwoven and difficult to separate. Our findings stand in contrast to the cognitivist "presumption that all psychological explanation must be framed in terms of internal mental representation, and processes" [14]. A consequence of this presumption is that material resources have no or low "cognitive value" [15, 16] or are something that is just "manipulated" [17]. Our study disproves this assumption. Furthermore, if tools and resources are taken into account it is common to see these as synonymous with "digital technologies". However, our study show that a focus only on "high-tech" resources would be problematic and that we in engineering education research should rather attempt to understand how students use many and varied bodily-material resources and in engineering education encourage their use [cf. 18, 19].

Moreover, we can in both cases see that the use of bodily-material resources transcended the boundaries of the individuals and became tools for the group's collaborative thinking, thereby fostering connection between individual cognition and collective re-cognition [cf. 20, 21, 22]. Thus, "distributed cognition" [23, 24] is clearly visible in our findings; achievements do not only arise from individuals thinking, but also through collaborative thinking distributed among the members in the teams *and* from the use of bodily-material resources.

It has not been possible for us in this short paper to give full justice the richness of our data and to explore all implications in depth. Given the apparent differences in the learning environments our results demonstrate that the role of bodily-material resources as cognitive tools in collaborative learning activities should be further investigated.

5 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Partial funding from the Swedish Research Council (Vetenskapsrådet) through grant VR 721-2011-5570, and the participation of the students at Aalborg and Linköping Universities are gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] Dillenbourg, P. (1999), What do you mean by collaborative learning?, in *Collaborative Learning: Cognitive and Computational Approaches.*, P. Dillenbourg, Ed. Elsevier, Oxford, pp. 1-19.
- [2] Stahl, G. (2013), Theories of Cognition in Collaborative Learning, in *The International Handbook of Collaborative Learning*, C. E. Hmelo-Silver, C. A. Chinn, C. K. K. Chan, and A. M. O'Donnell, Eds. Routledge, New York, NY, pp. 74-90.
- [3] Davidsen, J. and Ryberg, T. (2017), "This is the size of one meter": Children's bodily-material collaboration, *International Journal of Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning*, Vol. 12, No. 1, pp. 65-90.
- [4] Juhl, J. and Lindegaard, H. (2013), Representations and Visual Synthesis in Engineering Design, *Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 102, No. 1, pp. 20-50.
- [5] Goodwin, C. (2018), *Co-operative Action*, Cambridge University Press, New York, NY.
- [6] Roth, W. M. and Jornet, A. (2017), *Understanding Educational Psychology: A Late Vygotskian, Spinozist Approach.*, Springer,
- [7] Freitas, E. d. and Sinclair, N. (2014), *Mathematics and the body: material entanglements in the classroom*, Cambridge University Press, New York.
- [8] Bernhard, J. (2015), A tool to see with or just something to manipulate? - Investigating engineering students' use of oscilloscopes in the laboratory, Proc. of the SEFI annual conference, Orleans.
- [9] Jordan, B. and Henderson, A. (1995), Interaction Analysis: Foundations and Practice, *The Journal of the Learning Sciences*, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp. 39-103.
- [10] ten Have, P. (2007), *Doing Conversation Analysis: A Practical Guide*, SAGE, Los Angeles.
- [11] Bernhard, J. (2010), Insightful learning in the laboratory: Some experiences from ten years of designing and using conceptual labs, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, Vol. 35, No. 3, pp. 271-287.
- [12] Goodwin, C. (2003), Pointing as situated practice, in *Pointing: Where language, culture and cognition meet*, S. Kita, Ed. Erlbaum, Mahwah, NJ, pp. 217-241.
- [13] Stubbs, S. T., "Design drawing in instructional design at Brigham Young University's center for instructional design: A case study," Brigham Young University, Provo, UT, 2006.
- [14] Still, A. and Costall, A. (1987), Introduction: In place of cognitivism, in *Cognitive psychology in question*, A. Still and A. Costall, Eds. Harvester Press, Brighton, pp. 1-16.
- [15] Lelas, S. (1993), Science as technology, *The British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, Vol. 44, No. 3, pp. 423-442.
- [16] Hucke, L. and Fischer, H. (2002), The link of theory and practice in traditional and in computer-based university laboratory experiments, in *Teaching and Learning in the Science Laboratory*, D. Psillos and H. Niedderer, Eds. Kluwer, Dordrecht, pp. 205-218.
- [17] Lunetta, V. N., Hofstein, A., and Clough, M. P. (2007), Learning and teaching in the school science laboratory, in *Handbook of research on science education*, S. Abell and N. Lederman, Eds. Lawrence Erlbaum, Mahwah, pp. 393-441.
- [18] Ryberg, T., Davidsen, J., and Hodgson, V. (2018), Understanding nomadic collaborative learning groups, *British Journal of Educational Technology*, Vol. 49, No. 2, pp. 235-247.
- [19] Sørensen, E. (2009), *The Materiality of Learning: Technology and Knowledge in Educational Practice*, Cambridge University Press,
- [20] Brereton, M. (2004), Distributed Cognition in Engineering Design: Negotiating between Abstract and Material Representations, in *Design Representation*, G. Goldschmidt and W. L. Porter, Eds. Springer, London, pp. 83-103.
- [21] Murphy, K. M., "Collaborative imagining: The interactive use of gestures, talk, and graphic representation in architectural practice," in *Semiotica* vol. 2005, ed, 2005, pp. 113-145.
- [22] Henderson, K. (1999), *On Line and On Paper: Visual Representations, Visual Culture, and Computer Graphics in Design Engineering*, The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA.
- [23] Goodwin, C. (1995), Seeing in Depth, *Social Studies of Science*, Vol. 25, No. 2, pp. 237-274.
- [24] Hutchins, E. (1995), *Cognition in the Wild*, The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA.